

The landscape history of Nyddfych, Swansea¹

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Lying south of the M4 nestled between Junctions 46 and 47 at Llangyfelach, are the remnants of a remarkable piece of old Swansea landscape. The farmlands of Llangyfelach are slowly being lost to housing developments, but one remarkable preservation exercise, The Penllergare Trust, has managed to secure for a leasehold term some protection of the land and afford some barrier to encroachment. The Trust's mission to conserve some of the estate parklands of the Dillwyn Llewelyn family is well known², but less well known are the actual landscape riches of the Afon Llan valley within the remit of the Trust which point to richer historic pickings related to the early history of the Swansea region.

The central core of the Llan valley skirts a hill which these days is known as Graig-neddfwch Wood or Banc Nyddfych depending on which OS map is your preference but most of us know it as Nyddfych³. The names for Nyddfych are many, giving a clue to the incredible antiquity of the name. The origins of the name and its journey through many spellings are discussed in detail in Jeff Childs' seminal article⁴. Although the valley is often referred to as Penllergare in reference to the original house and estate of the Dillwyn Llewelyn family, my story here largely focusses on the older lands south of the original house which are predominantly Nyddfych.

Anyone who walks through the valley will eventually be drawn to the hill of Nyddfych. The rewards for the climb up are the beautiful views over the valley woodland and north Swansea. I still treasure the memory of the first trip up to Nyddfych led by David⁵, the indomitable woodsman who looks after the valley. At a fast pace only apparent in Welsh hill farmers I was taken on an all-day trip around the valley compressed into a couple of hours, as David felt I should see all. That first impression still lives with me, the valley is beautiful, but the phenomenon is Nyddfych.

For anyone who has a view of the land shaped by the teaching and writing of Oliver Rackham⁶, the woodlands of Nyddfych are a treasure house of delight and for me the focus of an obsession of detail for 8 years. As part of my professional work and following the so-called 'spatial turn' movement in the humanities, I resolved to research and record the landscape history via the various technologies of geographic information systems (GIS)⁷. So, instead of a book, for me, the lands of Nyddfych are recorded in a hundred layers of data and stories covering the trees, the animals, and the land shapes. This kind of deep mapping approach was pioneered by historians such as Rowland Parker⁸ and Gillian Tindall⁹ and particularly the inspirational work by Richard Leach Heat-Moon¹⁰. The rapid developments in technology mean that the promise of such approaches to geography and history are now becoming more accessible and exciting. In a similar vein, the remarkable book *Cartographies of Culture*¹¹ has brought significant Welsh literature to a new audience via digital mapping and spatial technique.

So, what you see here is a trip through my GIS¹² system of the trees of the beautiful landscape around Nyddfych. There is a precedent here. My original landscape work on Parliamentary enclosure and the eighteenth-century trees of Townhill¹³ which was published under the vision of Dr John Alban as Swansea City Archivist is a direct digital ancestor of this

work. The premise is always that heritage and history is more than buildings and structures, they can be living things that surround us and are part of our heritage and biodiversity. We have a duty of care and understanding.

Getting to Nyddfwch is a 20-minute walk from the current Penllergare Trust car park. The main path into the valley follows the course of the 1830 Carriage Drive which was a grand entrance into the estate from Cadle in the south offering lovely views of the newly created lakes and planting schemes created in the 1830s. The map shows the main routes.

The history of land ownership of Nyddfwch is beautifully summarised in Jeff Childs' study of land ownership in Llangyfelach¹⁴. Suffice to say that the area had a long history of settlement and land use up until the 1820s when the house was finally abandoned and dismantled. The landscape reflects the long occupancy of the land.

The main paths up onto the hill are all old, I've talked about the 1830 Carriage Drive already and the other two main routes are easily medieval or earlier in origin. The best preserved is the southern route which I call the Nyddfwch Road. The road fascinates me. Roads always do. This little fragment of road was in regular use from at least the 1200s until Nyddfwch was abandoned in the 1820s. This was more than a road to the farmhouse; it must have also been a way into the valley. It has width and structure to ensure it is not temporary. Big earth banks on both sides protect the road from snow and rain and protect the road as it came up from an even older road that forded the river down at Cadle. The banks on the uphill side are often enhanced with stone, large pebbles of sandstone and quartzite with occasional old red sandstone from the Brecon Beacons.

If there is one thing that suggests antiquity it is the makeup of these walls. Built of stones picked up from the surrounding land centuries ago. No angular quarry rock or traditional field walls here. The stones here are commonly sandstones of the rusty brown type of the coal measures, grey mudstones, and white quartzite pebbles and conglomerates. The occasional dark red pebble an unmistakable sign of old red sandstone brought down the valley from the Brecon Beacons by glaciers.

There is one thing missing. Slag (whether from copper or iron smelting), the ubiquitous building and repair material that marks the early Industrial Revolution in Swansea. These walls were made long before slag appeared.

Only about 200 metres of the road survives. Much is now under fields to the west, including the original link to the old Turnpike road from Cadle. That link disappeared two centuries ago. The piece that survives is the best part. Heavily banked with some wonderful marker trees and a sharp turn at the old reservoir before the short climb up to what would have been the courtyard of the Nyddfwch settlement.

The road originally came around the hillside of the mountain from what was to become (by the 1760s) the Swansea to Carmarthen Turnpike. It took a right turn into the river valley just beyond Turnpike Milestone 4 (4 miles to Swansea). It looks a strange deviation on a modern map, but it was the first easy route into the valley past the Cadle ford, missing the awkwardness of the little valley of the Bryn Dafydd stream, still a significant flow of water today.

Walking up the road from the Old Reservoir and as you look up the hill your eye naturally rests on the biggest tree. A multi-stemmed tree in winter, although in summer it's a glorious mass of leaves so you couldn't tell what was under there. Guarding the hill, you must pass through its presence to get to the top. This is Tree No.1. The first tree I surveyed up here.

It's a Sycamore. In some purist botanical circles that's enough to damn it to eradication or some sort of oblivion! I remember laughing out loud when I first read the slightly caustic sentence from Oliver Rackham... "The oft repeated statement that the Romans introduced sycamore is based on no evidence." Sycamore is a Swansea plant as much as Japanese Knotweed. I often see the two of them growing together round here. Both can tolerate the dirt, waste, and pollution of industrial Swansea, so maybe it's not so surprising.

In England, Sycamore gets a mention as early as the 1570s. A century later it has a bad reputation for gardens because of the sticky honeydew it drips. As a pioneer plant with a 'weedy' nature it will turn up in waste ground anywhere. The area in the north of the valley known as Bluebell Wood (a modern name invention), has a small field of young sycamores that have sprung up simultaneously since the 1950s.

Sycamore became popular as a hedgerow tree from the early 1700s. All the big Nyddfych sycamores are hedgerow 'specimens,' although a few younger ones are trying to establish themselves amongst the bracken and birch regeneration on the hill. The big old sycamores are different, they were planted where people wanted them. The oldest trees on the hill were likely planted in the final years of the eighteenth century or maybe by the 1820s. The hedges of Nyddfych have a lot of Sycamore, possibly planned as a quicker growing replacement in gaps created by local harvesting of the hedgerow oak. For centuries, Coal mining in the valley regularly stripped the land of all its usable timber and many trees were planted as a crop. Older field boundaries around Melin Llan further north also have sycamore as hedge trees.

Sycamore is a survivor. Illustrated beautifully by Tree No. 1 with all its scars and scorch marks. Its highly likely that most of the sycamore trees that were ever successfully planted are still alive. The Nyddfych sycamores have survived generations of fires and occasional cutting and pruning. They've earned their right to be there.

Trees don't read rules. Although Tree No.1 is not 'officially old', as far as Nyddfych is concerned it is old...one of the oldest. In fact, I think any tree with a diameter over 80cm in the Nyddfych area is going to be among the oldest living things we have around because people have chopped down everything bigger or older. The whole of the Llan valley could have been deforested many times since the Romans left.

The Nyddfych sycamores were planted on hedgerows as part of wider replanting of the hill. We do have some useful but tantalisingly scarce evidence from the journals of Lewis Weston Dillwyn.¹⁵ In the early nineteenth century, it was a tree of fashion and it was also a quick growing source of timber. Having taken the opportunity over the years to count the growth rings on any felled trees I can find in the valley, I know that the last great harvesting of hedgerow oak took place in the 1820s and 1830s. Many of the big oaks of the valley's hedgerows were cut or coppiced leaving a short trunk to regenerate. That's why so many of the surviving oaks we have in the area have multi stems as they have regrown from root stocks that could be up to 800 years old. Coppicing is a woodsman's practice of regenerating timber that goes back centuries. Harvesting of oak will inevitably create gaps on banks and in hedges. The sycamore was the perfect tree for the gaps.

Although sycamore has a reputation for tenacious growth as secondary woodland (I've seen it on Berlin bombsites and Lower Swansea Valley slag heaps) it seems to have had limited spread on the hill. The hedgerow specimens mostly look resilient and hardy, but the occasional spread into surrounding woodland has resulted in some quite sickly specimens although they do often provide some spectacular hollow trunk habitat appreciated by the local bats.

So, anything with a trunk diameter over 80cm is old...valley old. It's a rough rule that works across northern Swansea. A simple reason... industrial and post-industrial Swansea (and Glamorgan) were stripped of 99% of their woodlands, many times. People underestimate the demand for timber during the industrial revolution, it wasn't just about coal around here. Regeneration of most of the woodland we see today has happened since the 1970s. The last really big trees on Nyddfwch and Carn Goch were cleared in the 1940s, some of the big trunks and stumps are still out there where they fell being the victims of Forestry Commission ruinous ringbarking or careless logging. The few old trees we have left were mostly too twisted, scarred, or inaccessible to be bothered with. Incredibly, the story so far means we probably have more trees on Nyddfwch today that there have been for 600 years.

The age and life experiences of Tree No.1 mean there's a lot more to it and its place in life on the Hill. The scars of burning, various diseases, and the decades of exposure to local people all leave a mark. The flaky bark and the trunk cavities supply shelter for all sorts of insects and plants. Although experts tell us that other more native trees support more life, the sycamore has over 40 insect associations and the massive numbers of sycamore aphids attract all sorts of insects and birds and bats. Tree No.1 is an important part of the biodiversity. Technically, any tree that shows such diversity in shape, scarring and micro-environments is called a 'veteran'...a recognition of what it's been through and what it can offer. Veteran trees are generally but, not always old. The lack of a range of veteran trees in our regenerating woodland landscapes (because they are still too young!), means we can never have diverse birdlife – owls like holes in trees for example. So, we can never go back to a normal woodland landscape...if we could ever know what that was. Sycamores on Nyddfwch rot fast leaving holes in their trunks and fall over in gales providing a quick supply of dead wood. So, sycamores can still fill a gap in need while oak woodlands are still maturing. Tree No. 1 is definitely a veteran of life on Nyddfwch.

The big trees of Nyddfwch are a mix of natural regeneration from the early eighteenth century and the added phases of planting by the estate owners from the 1800s. The scars in the land as depicted on recent LiDAR surveys suggest that the flanks of the hill were extensively damaged by coal workings leaving piles of mining waste and bad drainage. Lewis Weston Dillwyn's journals mention drainage work as well as his planting¹⁶. It seems likely the land was extensively planted to obscure the coal tips and workings. Some of those trees survive today as significant ancients.

Most people walking up onto the Hill will arrive via the Carriage Drive and take a right turn up the hill path at the first opportunity just past the signposted ruins of Middle Lodge. This is another old road and probably served as the link between the old water mill¹⁷ and Nyddfwch farmhouse. It could have had another use as a route for ponies to take baskets of coal out of the valley.

The sad thing to remember about the landscape of Nyddfwch and the wider Penllergare Valley is that it is special because it has survived. With the exception of some of the beautiful pines and redwoods planted by the Dillwyn-Llewelyns, there is nothing exceptional about the mix of trees and woodland in the area...apart from the sobering fact that it has usually been destroyed almost everywhere else in this part of the county. It puts a big obligation on us to ensure it survives further for future generations.

What follows is a trip through only some of the wonderful features in and around Nyddfwch. You will find many more.

Map 1. A general layout of the modern site of Nyddfwch inside the confines of the Penllergare Trust country park. The early medieval Nyddfwch would have been far larger. The northern boundaries of the coloured land on this map look to have been set by Lewis

Weston Dillwyn's planting scheme in 1819. The principal trees I have mentioned are also plotted here. The base plan is a LiDAR¹⁸ survey of the area from 2016.

Map 2. A closeup of the LiDAR plot of the land surface on part of Nyddfych. At the top you can see the disturbed land surfaces characteristic of coal mining disruption from the 1700s compared with the smoother surfaces of undisturbed woodland in the lower half of the picture. The coal areas are now heavily disguised under woodland and rhododendron growth.

Photo 1. The road to Nyddfwch from the south. An incredible survival from medieval times, the road here is flanked by a big bank on the downhill side with an ancient marker oak. Later additions of sycamores from the 1820s are starting to hollow supplying priceless habitat for biodiversity. In the far distance Tree No. 1 signals the approach to the original Nyddfwch courtyard. Which would have been up on the left.

Photo 2. Tree No. 1 on the Nyddfwch road in winter 2014. A beautiful veteran sycamore which could have been planted in the 1820s as part of the Lewis Weston Dillwyn work. One of the loveliest ancient sycamores I've ever surveyed. It's a hotspot for bat activity as well.

Photo 3. The Reservoir Sycamore. This is another tree planted in the 1820s. It marks the corner of the little reservoir that was probably built in the early 1800s. Now mostly silted up, it's another biodiversity hotspot.

Photo 4. Ancient stump. The woodlands have been harvested for usable timber many times. The last heavy felling was in the 1940s. You can see large stumps throughout the valley. Their longevity is remarkable, and they contribute good quantities of deadwood to the valley biodiversity.

Photo 5. Ringbarking. In the 1950s, the standard Forestry Commission method of killing an unwanted tree was to cut the living wood of the tree in a ring, the tree quickly dies. You can see many ringbarked oaks around the valley including some that are still standing, although long dead. It serves as a reminder that ecological management has changed and is likely to change far more in the future.

Photo 6. The Dear Oak. This tree is an incredible survivor and I simply do not understand how as its location is incredibly vulnerable. I have a photograph of this tree in full leaf in 1945. Its sinuous form suggests it is native local hedgerow oak rather than any plantation trees. It was originally on a hedge bank that ran down to the river side. The Nyddfwch Oak in Photo 7 is on the same bank. These marker oaks may have been deliberately planted on a

significant property boundary. The tree is in a healthy post-mature stage and is a good example of why we should be valuing ancient trees and their long post-mature lifecycles.

Photo 7. A closeup of the magnificent trunk of the Nyddfych Oak. This oak marks an old route into the meadow fields that ran alongside the Afon Llan in the eighteenth century. It is

on the same hedge bank as the Deer Oak in photo 6 which is about 200m west up the hillside. It has shed several large branches over the decades which means its 'deadwood biodiversity zone' is huge.

Photo 8. The Watermill Oak. This ancient tree is just north of the remains of the medieval watermill. Although many changes have happened around the tree including alteration of land levels in the nineteenth century, this tree survives.

Photo 9. The Boathouse Oak. So-called because it is near to the nineteenth-century boathouse that existed on the western side of the ornamental lake (the ruins can be seen today). It's a hedgerow oak of incredible age on a bank that is mostly buried under newer land surfaces related to the roads and sewer works of the valley floor.

Photo 10. The Open Oak. One of the most enigmatic trees on Nyddfwch. It's an open-grown tree that has naturally spread its branches with no restrictions or cutting. It's on the northern side of the original road from Nyddfwch farmhouse down to the old watermill. It's a big tree and it's hard to imagine that this was from one of the early planting schemes of the 1820s. My current view is that it is a natural regeneration tree from the eighteenth century that grew in the right place and as a native welsh oak it made an unattractive timber tree for harvesting.

Photo 11. The Octopus Oak. The incredible contorted base of an oak tree that has been coppiced over centuries. The tree may be 800 years old but successive harvesting of timber has rejuvenated the original tree. The shape of the rootstock suggests it may have been on a hedge bank or possibly on the banks of a large stream that ran down from the coal mining site on the hillside above.

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- ¹ Robins, N.A., 'The landscape history of Nyddfych (Penlle'rgaer), *Minerva The Swansea History Journal*, 29, 2021.
- ² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Penllergare> (Accessed February 2021).
- ³ You will find the hill called Nyddfych, Nedeveu, Nydeueuh, and Nedevue. The best summary of the names is in Childs, J., *The Parish of Llangyfelach*, (Swansea, 2018), 105.
- ⁴ Childs, J., 'In Search of Nyddfych,' *Gower*, 51, 2000, 53-70.
- ⁵ David Connick is a conservation and woodland expert for the Penllergare Trust.
- ⁶ See Rackham, O., *Trees, and woodland in the British landscape*, (London, 1990), or *The History of the Countryside*, (London, 1986).
- ⁷ A geographic information system (GIS) is a framework for gathering, managing, and analysing data. Rooted in the science of geography, GIS integrates many types of data.
- ⁸ Parker, R., *The Common Stream*, (London, 1976). A beautiful piece of village history.
- ⁹ Tindall, G., *The Fields Beneath: the history of one London village* (London, 1977).
- ¹⁰ Heat-Moon, William Least, *PrairyErth (a deep map)*, (New York, 1991).
- ¹¹ Davies, Damian Walford, *Cartographies of Culture. New Geographies of Welsh Writing in English*, (Cardiff, 2012).
- ¹² I prefer to use QGIS as it is a free and open-source cross-platform desktop geographic information system application that supports viewing, editing, and analysis of geospatial data.
- ¹³ Robins, Nigel A., *The Enclosure of Townhill*, (Swansea, 1991), Townhill in central Swansea was enclosed from common land by a 1762 Enclosure act. Despite the substantial building that has taken place since the 1920s, a large number of trees and associated landscape still survives.
- ¹⁴ See Childs, (n. 1 above), 64-5, 106-7.
- ¹⁵ For example, see The Journals of Lewis Weston Dillwyn (b.1778 d.1855), <https://www.swansea.ac.uk/media/2VOL-18X.pdf> 9 (accessed February 2021), In February 1819, Dillwyn was supervising plantation and drainage work on Nyddfych, the extent of the planting is shown on the OS One-Inch Old Series Sheet 37 (1830).
- ¹⁶ See Dillwyn's Journal entry (n. 12 above) 6 March 1819.
- ¹⁷ References to the old mill are scarce, even though a significant structure still remains at the side of the Afon Llan. See Rogers, W.C., *Historic Swansea*, (Swansea, 2005) 187, and Taylor, B.S., The watermills of the Lordship of Gower (Part Two), *Gower*, 50, 1999, 20-37.
- ¹⁸ (LiDAR) is an airborne mapping technique, which uses a laser to measure the distance between the aircraft and the ground. Up to 100,000 measurements per second are made of the ground, allowing highly detailed surface and terrain models to be generated at different spatial resolutions. LiDAR data in Wales is freely accessible via the Lle Geoportol, <https://lle.gov.wales/home?lang=en> (accessed February 2021).